

Kinetics of Vapour Phase Oxidation of 1-Phenylethanol over Ferric Molybdate Catalyst

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Kinetics of the vapour phase oxidation of 1-phenylethanol over ferric molybdate was studied in an isothermal, differential, fixed-bed reactor in the temperature range 240-300°. The sole product obtained was acetophenone. Twentyfour different models including redox, Langmuir-Hinshelwood and Rideal were examined to fit the experimental data. These models were compared and the redox model was found to be more satisfactory than the others.

CHEMISTRY of the catalytic processes, employed in industry are poorly understood. Also many of them bear little similarity to the methods used for preparing the same chemicals in the organic chemical laboratory.

Hoping that some of the well tested methods of physical organic chemistry could be applied for the study of heterogeneous catalytic reactions we started the present programme of work. In the study of catalytic reactions the emphasis is on the processes taking place on the surface of the catalyst. We thought we could focus our attention on the substrate and the detailed transformations it was going through before being converted to the product. We hope that it would lead to a deeper understanding of the chemical processes involved and possibly also throw light on some of the features of interaction between the substrate and the catalyst.

Oxidation of alcohols under homogeneous conditions is well studied. The mechanism of oxidation by a number of reagents like chromic acid, hypobromous acid, single electron oxidants like Ce^{IV} nitrate, etc., has been fairly well understood.

One could write at least three distinct possibilities.

In the present study of which this paper forms a part, we have examined the oxidation of 1-phenylethyl alcohols over ferric molybdate which is a selective catalyst for the vapour phase oxidation of aliphatic alcohols to carbonyl compounds¹⁻⁶.

Experimental

Apparatus, materials and methods: An all-glass apparatus consisting mainly of alcohol mixer, preheater, reactor and product collection unit (a series of bubblers and double surface condensers) was used. A schematic diagram of the apparatus used is shown in Fig. 1. The reactor (30 cm $\times$ 2 cm dia.) had a perforated glass plate as catalyst support. Heating was accomplished in all cases with externally wound Kanthal (nichrome resistance) heating wire. The power input to the system at various points in the set-up was controlled by variable auto-transformers and simmerstats and the temperature was measured by a calibrated chromel-alumel thermocouple.

The materials consisted of distilled 1-phenylethanol (Fluka, A.G.), nitrogen of purity 99% in cylinder (Indian Oxygen) and air. Nitrogen and air drawn from the compressed air line were purified from the entrained oil, moisture and carbon dioxide. The gases were metered at ambient conditions of 0.899 std. atm and 25°. The ferric molybdate catalyst was prepared from ferric nitrate and ammonium paramolybdate as described by Kolovertnov *et al.*⁷ The physical properties of the catalyst are listed in Table 1.

A known amount of the catalyst contained in the reactor was first purged with nitrogen at the desired temperature. Vapours of alcohols were oxidised over the catalyst in the reactor in a current of air and nitrogen. Samples were collected for analysis when the catalyst bed temperature had remained constant and steady state was reached. The only

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Fig. 1. Flow diagram. Experimental set up.

1 Nitrogen cylinder, 2 Compressed air reservoir, 8 Pressure compensating drum, 4 Air and nitrogen purifying towers, 5 Capillary flow meter for air, 6 Capillary flow meter for nitrogen, 7 Manometric fluid collector, 8 Alcohol reservoir, 9 Capillary flow meter for alcohol, 10 Mixer, 11 Preheater, 12 Reactor, 13 Catalyst bed, 14 Condenser cum bubbler train, 15 Ice cooled absorber train, 16 Capillary flow meter for vent gas, 17 To gas sampler, 18 Pressure control valve, V Needle valve, T Two-way stop cock, TS Three-way stop cock, M Manometer, TC Thermocouple, I1 Inlet for alcohol, I2 Inlet for nitrogen, I3 Inlet for air.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF CATALYST

BET surface area, $m^2 g^{-1}$	0.7
Average particle diameter, μ	192
Bulk density, $g cm^{-3}$	1.55
Particle density, $g cm^{-3}$	3.5
Pore volume, $cm^3 g^{-1}$	0.025
Average pore radius, Å	714

reaction product acetophenone was confirmed by tlc and spectroscopic analyses. An Orsat gas analysis of the exit gas indicated that the amounts of carbon dioxide and carbon monoxide formed were insignificant. The product acetophenone was quantitatively estimated by measuring the intensity of the colour of its complex with 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine⁸. The amount of unreacted 1-phenylethanol was estimated similarly by complexing with ceric ammonium nitrate⁹. The effects of partial pressures of alcohol and oxygen on the rate of reaction are tabulated in Tables 2 and 3.

Before carrying out preliminary studies, a thermodynamic analysis of the reaction under study, *i.e.*

revealed the irreversible nature of the reaction as at 300° the equilibrium constant is 4.8×10^{21} .

Diffusion effects: Experiments were conducted to find the regions in which resistance due to physical

transport phenomena (inter- and intra-phase mass diffusion) do not influence the reaction rate. It was found that above a feed flow rate of $200 l h^{-1}$ the effect of interphase diffusion on reaction rate was insignificant and with catalyst particle size of 440μ and lower intraphase diffusion rate did not influence the reaction rate. The results are depicted in Figs. 2 and 3. In the actual kinetic runs, feed flow rates of the order of $400 l h^{-1}$ and catalyst particle size of 192μ were employed. The effect of time factor and life of the catalyst on conversion is shown in Figs. 4 and 5. The influence of interphase diffusion was tested by the method of Yoshida *et al.*¹⁰ corresponding to the values of the following variables at 300°.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Modified Reynolds no. (Re)} &= 0.47 \\
 \text{Schmidt no. (Sc)} &= 2.17 \\
 \text{Rate no. (R)} &= 2.60 \times 10^{-8}
 \end{aligned}$$

The ratio of partial pressure difference of reactant between bulk phase and catalyst surface to the partial pressure in the bulk phase was found to be 1.14×10^{-6} indicating the absence of external diffusional effects. The intraparticle diffusional effect was checked by Weisz and Hick's method¹¹. For the Thiele type modulus of 0.15, the effectiveness factor is unity and this shows the insignificant nature of intraparticle diffusion.

Kinetic analysis: The conversion in most cases was below 11% except at the maximum temperature of 300°. The error involved in assuming differential reactor analysis was found¹² to be 1%. The initial

Fig. 2. Effect of external diffusion.

Fig. 3. Effect of internal diffusion.

rates were calculated using the approximate equation (1).

$$\text{Initial rate} = \frac{[\text{mean rate}]}{[\text{initial conc. of reactant}]} \times \frac{[\text{initial conc. of reactant}]}{[\text{mean conc. of reactant}]} \quad (1)$$

As θ , the relative concentration of surface oxygen taking part in both the stages of redox model, is fairly constant in the experimental conditions covered, the use of equation (1) in calculating the initial rate is justified. The initial rates thus calculated were compared with the experimental rates and it was found that the overall deviation was less

than 6%. The above analysis gives a good justification for using a differential reactor analysis. The rate equation for the analysis of the data can be expressed as

$$-r_A = dx_A/d[W/F_A] \quad (2)$$

Results and Discussion

Recent literature on vapour phase oxidation using transition metal oxides as catalysts has shown that a redox mechanism operates in a number of cases^{1,2-15}. According to this model the oxidation proceeds by simultaneous reduction of the catalyst

Fig. 4. Effect of time-factor on conversion.

surface by the reactant and reoxidation by oxygen in the bulk phase. The mechanism can be represented as

where C_{-ox} and C_{-red} represent the oxidised and reduced forms of the catalyst, respectively. The rate equation based on the above mechanism adapted to the present system can be given as

$$-r_A = \frac{k_d k_o p_A^2 p_O}{k_o p_O^2 + N k_d p_A} \quad (3)$$

Experiments were planned to test the redox model. The runs were conducted in a steady state isothermal flow reactor. Tables 2 and 3 show typical data along with the experimental rates. The two-stage redox equation (3) was coupled with the mass

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF PARTIAL PRESSURE OF ALCOHOL ON RATE AT CONSTANT OXYGEN PARTIAL PRESSURE*

Temp. °C	Initial alcohol partial pressure, std. atm	Time factor (g)(h)mol ⁻¹	Conversion %	Rate × 10 ⁴ (mol/h)(g)
240	0.0028	166.70	1.77	1.06
	0.0060	77.81	1.71	2.21
	0.0090	51.41	1.66	3.22
	0.0100	44.85	1.57	3.54
255	0.0028	166.92	2.92	1.75
	0.0060	77.81	2.81	3.64
	0.0090	51.38	2.73	5.32
	0.0100	44.44	2.60	5.85
270	0.0028	166.74	4.65	2.79
	0.0060	77.42	4.51	5.82
	0.0090	51.44	4.39	8.51
	0.0100	44.35	4.16	9.38
285	0.0028	166.18	7.21	4.84
	0.0060	77.65	7.04	9.06
	0.0090	51.54	6.64	13.80
	0.0100	44.37	6.50	14.60
300	0.0028	166.40	10.78	6.48
	0.0060	77.58	10.54	13.60
	0.0090	51.49	10.28	20.00
	0.0100	44.42	9.79	22.00

* Catalyst : ferric molybdate ; oxygen partial pressure : 0.0068 std. atm , total flow rate : 800 l h⁻¹ , total pressure : 0.899 std. atm.

Fig. 5. Effect of life of catalyst on conversion.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF PARTIAL PRESSURE OF OXYGEN ON RATE AT CONSTANT ALCOHOL PARTIAL PRESSURE*

Temp. °C	Initial oxygen partial pressure, std. atm	Time factor (g)(h)mol ⁻¹	Conversion %	Rate × 10 ⁴ (mol/h)(g)
240	0.0045	77.95	1.79	2.29
	0.0026	77.22	1.79	2.28
	0.0014	77.89	1.67	2.15
	0.0007	77.82	1.58	2.03
256	0.0045	77.74	2.94	3.78
	0.0026	77.49	2.86	3.69
	0.0014	77.66	2.76	3.56
	0.0007	77.58	2.61	3.36
270	0.0045	77.55	4.69	6.05
	0.0026	77.65	4.58	5.90
	0.0014	77.47	4.42	5.71
	0.0007	77.53	4.19	5.40
285	0.0045	77.56	7.81	9.43
	0.0026	77.58	7.14	9.21
	0.0014	77.48	6.90	8.91
	0.0007	77.49	6.52	8.42
300	0.0045	77.59	10.96	14.1
	0.0026	77.56	10.73	13.8
	0.0014	77.57	10.39	13.4
	0.0007	77.49	9.81	12.7

* Catalyst : ferric molybdate ; alcohol partial pressure : 0.0063 std. atm ; total flow rate : 800 l-h⁻¹ , total pressure : 0.899 std. atm.

conservation equation (2), and was integrated for four combinations of reaction orders m and n, viz. [1, 1], [0.5, 1], [0.5, 0.5] and [1, 0.5]. The four integrated rate equations can be written as

$$-1/\bar{r}_A = 1k_A \bar{p}_A + N/k_O \bar{p}_O \quad (4)$$

for m = n = 1

$$\bar{p}_A = \frac{P_{A_i} - P_{A_f}}{\ln[P_{A_i}/P_{A_f}]} \quad (5)$$

$$\bar{p}_O = \frac{P_{O_i} - P_{O_f}}{\ln[P_{O_i}/P_{O_f}]} \quad (6)$$

for m = n = 0.5

$$\bar{p}_A = \frac{P_{A_i}^{0.5} + P_{A_f}^{0.5}}{2} \quad (7)$$

$$\bar{p}_O = \frac{P_{O_i}^{0.5} + P_{O_f}^{0.5}}{2} \quad (8)$$

where $p_{A_f} = p_{A_i}[1 - x_A]$, and $p_{O_f} = p_{O_i} - Np_{A_i}x_A$.

Along with the redox model, some other models were also tested for their validity for the present system. These are listed in Table 4. Initial rate data were used for testing these models. The parameters were estimated from the linearised equations of the models using the method of least squares. The parameters of the models thus estimated are included in Table 5.

Comparison of various models : For distinguishing among the different models use is made of the following criteria.

- (i) Since all constants represent some chemical process they should have positive values to satisfy physical reality.
- (ii) All constants should exhibit temperature sensitivity and be capable of being fitted to an Arrhenius type equation from which activation energies of reaction, adsorption, etc., can be evaluated.
- (iii) A given model should give a good fit to the experimental data.

The models were evaluated using these criteria and the conclusions drawn are summarised in Table 6. It was found that only the two-stage redox models with order combinations [1, 1 ; model 1] and [1, 0.5 ; model 4] satisfy all the criteria. Therefore, all other models were rejected.

TABLE 4—MODELS OTHER THAN TWO STAGE REDOX MODEL TESTED FOR 1-PHENYLETHANOL OXIDATION

Model no ^a	Model	Model equation
5-8	Steady state adsorption model with additional assumption that the oxygen desorption rate is not negligible	$-r_A = \frac{k_A k'_O p_A^m p_O^n}{N k_A p_A^n + k'_O p_O^n + k_A}$
9-12	Rideal model	$-r_A = \frac{k K_O p_O^m p_A^n}{1 + K_O p_O^n}$
13-16	Langmuir Hinshelwood model (surface reaction controlling)	$-r_A = \frac{k K_A K_O p_O^m p_A^n}{[1 + k_O p_O^n + k_A p_A^m]^2}$
17-20	Langmuir Hinshelwood model (surface reaction controlling, oxygen dissociatively adsorbed)	$-r_A = \frac{k K_A p_A^m \sqrt{K_O p_O^n}}{[1 + K_A p_A^m + \sqrt{K_O p_O^n}]^2}$
21-24	Empirical model	$-r_A = k p_A^m p_O^n$

* Under each category the four models are respectively, where m=1, n=1 ; m=0.5, n=1 ; m=0.5, n=0.5 and m=1, n=0.5.

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TABLE 5—CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS MODELS BASED ON INITIAL RATE

(Table 5 contd.)

Model no.	Temp. °C	Values of parameters			Av. abs. devn.	(Table 5 contd.)							
		k_A	k_O			$(kK_A K_O)^{0.5}$	$(kK_O/K_A)^{0.5}$	$(kK_A/K_O)^{0.5}$					
1	240	8.84 E-2*	8.16 E-1		6.32 E 0	240	9.40 E 0	8.08 E-1	2.19 E-2	1.17 E+1			
	255	6.87 E-2	1.88 E 0		8.87 E 0	255	1.41 E+1	9.91 E-1	2.81 E-2	1.05 E+1			
	270	1.03 E-1	2.82 E 0		8.95 E 0	270	1.54 E+1	5.16 E-1	8.67 E-2	1.79 E+1			
	285	1.62 E-1	3.70 E 0		6.59 E 0	285	1.92 E+1	6.68 E-1	4.48 E-2	1.39 E+1			
	300	2.47 E-1	5.85 E 0		7.77 E 0	300	2.35 E+1	8.80 E-1	5.54 E-2	1.14 E+1			
2	240	1.61 E-4	-2.50 E-2		1.47 E+1	14	210	1.30 E-1	-1.29 E-2	1.58 E-3	1.22 E+1		
	255	2.67 E-4	-4.10 E-2		1.38 E+1		255	1.07 E-1	-1.65 E-2	2.03 E-3	1.34 E+1		
	270	4.28 E-4	-6.46 E-2		2.34 E+1		270	2.11 E-1	-2.09 E-2	2.57 E-3	1.42 E+1		
	285	6.70 E-4	-1.01 E-1		3.24 E+1		285	2.68 E-1	-2.61 E-2	3.22 E-3	1.25 E+1		
	300	1.01 E-3	-1.50 E-1		1.51 E+1		300	3.22 E-1	-3.19 E-2	3.98 E-3	1.37 E+1		
3	240	1.91 E-4	-3.70 E-4		1.68 E+1	15	240	3.42 E-2	-3.65 E-3	6.57 E-3	4.74 E 0		
	255	2.16 E-4	-5.45 E-4		2.81 E+1		255	9.41 E-2	-4.49 E-3	8.44 E-3	3.26 E 0		
	270	3.46 E-4	-8.68 E-4		2.42 E+1		270	5.58 E-2	-5.92 E-3	1.07 E-2	3.76 E 0		
	285	5.41 E-4	-1.35 E-3		1.78 E+1		285	6.97 E-2	-7.39 E-3	1.33 E-2	1.57 E 0		
	300	8.16 E-4	-2.01 E-3		1.77 E+1		300	8.55 E-2	-9.04 E-3	1.64 E-2	1.03 E 0		
4	240	3.99 E-2	2.03 E-2		8.25 E-2	16	240	1.68 E 0	1.14 E-1	9.72 E-2	3.51 E 0		
	255	6.62 E-2	3.43 E-2		5.06 E-2		255	2.17 E 0	1.47 E-1	1.25 E-1	3.75 E 0		
	270	1.06 E-1	5.78 E-2		2.87 E-2		270	2.76 E 0	1.97 E-1	1.58 E-1	3.38 E 0		
	285	1.63 E-1	9.26 E-2		2.66 E-2		285	3.46 E 0	2.57 E-1	1.98 E-1	3.91 E 0		
	300	2.55 E-1	1.48 E-1		3.39 E-2		300	4.26 E 0	3.45 E-1	2.45 E-1	3.23 E 0		
5	240	3.76 E-2	2.36 E-1	-9.90 E+1	2.05 E 0	17	Numerically corresponds to model 16 rate constant combinations.						
	255	6.25 E-2	3.98 E-1	-1.63 E+2	2.07 E 0		18	Numerically corresponds to model 15 rate constant combinations.					
	270	1.01 E-1	6.72 E-1	-2.37 E+2	2.53 E 0			19	240	1.77 E-2	-1.95 E-3	1.35 E-2	9.57 E 0
	285	1.59 E-1	1.11 E 0	-4.72 E+2	1.94 E 0				255	2.23 E-2	-2.50 E-3	1.73 E-2	9.53 E 0
	300	2.43 E-1	1.88 E 0	-8.24 E+2	1.82 E 0				270	2.89 E-2	-3.16 E-3	2.17 E-2	9.47 E 0
6	240	2.02 E-4	-4.81 E-4	1.21 E-2	1.55 E+1	285			3.61 E-2	-3.95 E-3	2.72 E-2	9.42 E 0	
	255	3.34 E-4	-7.98 E-4	2.01 E-2	1.56 E+1	300	4.43 E-2		-4.83 E-3	3.32 E-2	9.33 E 0		
	270	5.36 E-4	-1.27 E-3	3.21 E-2	1.57 E+1	20	240	6.88 E-1	6.69 E-2	2.93 E-1	4.63 E 0		
	285	8.41 E-4	-1.99 E-3	5.01 E-2	1.61 E+1		255	6.91 E-1	8.64 E-2	2.98 E-1	4.54 E 0		
	300	1.27 E-3	-2.99 E-3	7.54 E-2	1.61 E+1		270	1.14 E 0	1.16 E-1	3.75 E-1	4.33 E 0		
7	240	1.96 E-4	-3.97 E-5	1.01 E-3	1.49 E+1		285	1.48 E 0	1.52 E-1	4.70 E-1	3.64 E 0		
	255	3.24 E-4	-6.58 E-5	1.68 E-3	1.49 E+1		300	1.76 E 0	2.07 E-1	5.78 E-1	4.21 E 0		
	270	5.18 E-4	-1.05 E-4	2.68 E-3	1.50 E+1	21	240	1.01 E+1			6.60 E+1		
	285	8.11 E-4	-1.64 E-4	4.19 E-3	1.51 E+1		255	1.68 E+1			6.61 E+1		
	300	1.22 E-3	-2.47 E-4	6.31 E-3	1.54 E+1		270	2.71 E+1			6.62 E+1		
8	240	4.00 E-2	2.13 E-2	9.60 E+1	3.55 E 0		285	4.28 E+1			6.63 E+1		
	255	6.63 E-2	3.53 E-2	2.63 E+2	4.41 E 0		300	6.54 E+1			6.64 E+1		
	270	1.07 E-1	6.05 E-2	2.93 E+2	3.57 E 0	22	240	6.30 E-2			7.90 E+1		
	285	1.63 E-1	1.00 E-1	2.74 E+2	1.47 E 0		255	1.04 E-1			7.92 E+1		
	300	2.57 E-1	1.71 E-1	2.49 E+2	2.15 E 0		270	1.68 E-1			7.94 E+1		
9	240	3.86 E-2	2.56 E+2		2.70 E+1		285	2.64 E-1			7.95 E+1		
	255	6.40 E-2	4.33 E+2		2.67 E+1		300	3.99 E-1			7.98 E+1		
	270	1.03 E-1	7.28 E+2		2.52 E+1	23	240	3.75 E-3			4.45 E+1		
	285	1.63 E-1	1.16 E+3		2.41 E+1		255	6.22 E-3			4.46 E+1		
	300	2.48 E-1	1.82 E+3		2.85 E+1		270	9.99 E-3			4.48 E+1		
10	240	1.64 E-4	-7.99 E-1		3.15 E+1		285	1.57 E-2			4.50 E+1		
	255	2.72 E-4	-1.13 E 0		3.13 E+1		300	2.38 E-2			4.53 E+1		
	270	4.36 E-4	-2.06 E 0		3.38 E+1	24	240	6.01 E-1			3.06 E+1		
	285	6.84 E-4	-3.21 E 0		3.20 E+1		255	9.98 E-1			3.07 E+1		
	300	1.03 E-3	-4.76 E 0		3.41 E+1		270	1.61 E 0			3.08 E+1		
11	240	1.46 E-4	-1.43 E-2		3.57 E+1		285	2.55 E 0			3.08 E+1		
	255	2.42 E-4	-2.35 E-2		3.65 E+1		300	3.89 E 0			3.09 E+1		
	270	3.87 E-4	-3.69 E-2		3.86 E+1	19	240	4.15 E-2	5.29 E 0		2.29 E+1		
	285	6.06 E-4	-5.76 E-2		3.83 E+1		255	6.89 E-2	8.96 E 0		2.27 E+1		
	300	9.13 E-4	-8.57 E-2		3.77 E+1		270	1.10 E-1	1.51 E+1		1.79 E+1		
12	240	1.46 E-4	-1.43 E-2		3.57 E+1		285	1.74 E-1	2.40 E+1		2.13 E+1		
	255	2.42 E-4	-2.35 E-2		3.65 E+1		300	2.64 E-1	3.80 E+1		2.01 E+1		
	270	3.87 E-4	-3.69 E-2		3.86 E+1								
	285	6.06 E-4	-5.76 E-2		3.83 E+1								
	300	9.13 E-4	-8.57 E-2		3.77 E+1								

* E+n indicates $\times 10^n$,
E-n indicates $\times 10^{-n}$.

TABLE 6 SUMMARY OF MODEL DISCRIMINATION BY CLASSICAL APPROACH

Model no.	Criteria		
	1	2	3
1	✓	✓	✓
2	✓	✓	✓
3	✓	✓	✓
4	✓	✓	✓
5	✓	✓	✓
6	✓	✓	✓
7	✓	✓	✓
8	✓	✓	✓
9	✓	✓	✓
10	✓	✓	✓
11	✓	✓	✓
12	✓	✓	✓
13	✓	✓	✓
14	✓	✓	✓
15	✓	✓	✓
16	✓	✓	✓
17	✓	✓	✓
18	✓	✓	✓
19	✓	✓	✓
20	✓	✓	✓
21	✓	✓	✓
22	✓	✓	✓
23	✓	✓	✓
24	✓	✓	✓

✓ satisfies criterion.
 × does not satisfy criterion.

A statistical method¹⁶ was employed to choose between the rival models. In this method, the magnitude of the non-intrinsic parameter λ , given by equation (9)

$$r - 0.5[r_1 + r_2] = \lambda[r_1 - r_2] + \xi \quad (9)$$

determines which of the two models represents the data adequately: if model 4 represents the data satisfactorily, then the confidence interval of λ includes -0.5 and model 1 is rejected, and *vice versa*, if the confidence interval of λ includes $+0.5$. The results summarised in Table 7 indicate that

TABLE 7—VALUES OF NON-INTRINSIC PARAMETER, λ

Temp. °C	λ	Standard error	Confidence interval of λ
240	-0.373	0.077	-0.184 to -0.560
255	-0.694	0.280	-0.181 to -1.257
270	-0.919	0.368	-0.031 to -1.607
285	-0.851	0.161	-0.467 to -1.244
300	-0.568	0.029	-0.497 to -0.639

model 4 is preferred to model 1 at all the temperatures, for the confidence interval of λ in none of these cases is anywhere near $+0.5$.

Graphical test for model 4: The plots of $[\bar{p}_A - \bar{r}_A]$ vs $[\bar{p}_A/\bar{p}_O]$ and $[\bar{p}_O - \bar{r}_A]$ vs $[\bar{p}_O/\bar{p}_A]$ for model 4 are shown in Figs. 6 and 7. These plots take into account the variation in the mean values of partial pressures of alcohol and oxygen. In these figures, the solid lines indicate the least squares fit. The linearity existing in these plots shows the validity of the two-stage redox model as well as the assumptions

Fig. 6. Plot of $(\bar{p}_A - \bar{r}_A)$ vs $(\bar{p}_A/\bar{p}_O)$.

Fig. 7. Plot of $(\bar{p}_O - \bar{r}_A)$ vs $(\bar{p}_O/\bar{p}_A)$.

TABLE 8—RATE CONSTANTS, BY LEAST SQUARES LINEAR AND NON-LINEAR REGRESSION

Temp. °C	$k_d \times 10^3$ mol/(h)(atm)		$k_o \times 10^6$ mol/(h)(g)(atm) ^{0.5}		Sum of squares of residuals	
	a	b	a	b	a × 10 ^{1.5}	b × 10 ^{1.5}
240	8.97	8.99	2.06	2.05	8.90	6.91
255	6.80	6.61	3.78	3.48	20.10	4.50
270	10.68	10.60	5.85	5.93	12.15	4.74
285	16.92	16.70	9.48	9.68	17.16	7.97
300	25.38	25.40	15.91	15.90	12.80	9.90

a = linear regression, b = nonlinear regression.

made regarding the order of the reaction, viz. $m=1$ and $n=0.5$.

Non-linear least squares estimation of parameters of selected model: The integrated rate equation representing the system is

$$\frac{1}{-r_d} = \frac{1}{k_d p_d} + \frac{N}{k_o p_o} \quad (10)$$

where $\bar{r}_d$ and $\bar{p}_o$ are given by equations (6) and (8). The rate constants in equation (10) were estimated using non-linear least squares method¹⁷. These values are incorporated in Table 8. It is seen from the table that the use of non-linear least squares technique has resulted in a decrease of sum of squares of residuals.

The rate constants when plotted (Fig. 8) showed that they followed Arrhenius law. In the non-linear estimation of activation energy and pre-exponential factor a reparametrized temperature was used¹⁸.

The Arrhenius equation was modified as

$$k = A' \exp [-E/R' T'] \quad (11)$$

$$\text{where } \frac{1}{T'} = \frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_0} \quad (12)$$

$$\text{and } \frac{1}{T'} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{i=1}^{n+1} \frac{1}{T_i} \quad (13)$$

ut in equation (13) represents the number of temperature levels. The activation energy and pre-exponential factor estimated by the non-linear method are given in Table 9.

TABLE 9—ACTIVATION ENERGIES AND ARRHENIUS FREQUENCY FACTORS

Parameter	Catalyst reduction step	Catalyst reoxidation step
E_a kcal mol ⁻¹	17.486	19.0
log A	20.900	20.6

Summary and conclusions: Vapour phase oxidation of 1-phenylethanol to acetophenone over ferric molybdate catalyst was studied in the temperature range 240-300° in the absence of inter- and intra-phase diffusion. The reaction is adequately described by the redox equation (14).

$$-\frac{1}{r_d} = \frac{1}{k_d p_d} + \frac{0.5}{k_o p_o^{0.5}} \quad (14)$$

It was observed that the catalyst reduction and reoxidation steps proceeded at comparable rates.

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Notation

- E_a activation energy, kcal mol⁻¹
- F_d flow rate of 1-phenylethanol, mole/hr
- K_d and K_o equilibrium constants for adsorption of 1-phenylethanol and adsorption of oxygen
- k overall reaction rate constant
- k_d rate constant for catalyst reduction step, mol/(g)(h)(atm)
- k_o rate constant for catalyst reoxidation step mol/(g)(h)(atm)^{0.5}
- k'_o and k_d adsorption and desorption rate constants of oxygen in order of reaction with respect to 1-phenylethanol

Fig. 8. Arrhenius plots

N moles of oxygen required to oxidize 1 mole of 1-phenylethanol
 n order of reaction with respect to oxygen
 p_A partial pressure of 1-phenylethanol, std. atm
 p_O partial pressure of oxygen, std. atm
 R rate number
 $-r$ observed rate of reaction
 $-r_A$ rate of reaction mole of 1-phenylethanol/(g)(h)
 Re Reynolds number
 Sc Schmidt number
 T temperature K
 W weight of catalyst, g
 x_A conversion, mole of 1-phenylethanol converted per mole fed
 λ non-intrinsic parameter
 ϵ random experimental error

Subscripts

i initial
 f final

Superscript

- mean value

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